

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHIDAGI NUQSONLI BOLALARDA MATEMATIKA MASHG'ULOTLARINI O'TKAZISH YO'LLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida tarbiyalanayotgan nuqsonli bolalarni rivojlantirishda matematikaning ahamiyati, pedagoglarning tajribalari va tarbiyalanuvchilarga aqliy jarayonlarni rivojlantirishda neyropsixologik kinesiologik yondashuvlar haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagog, neyropsixologik, kinesiologik, sensorika.

WAYS OF CONDUCTING MATHEMATICS LESSONS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH DEFECTS

Abstract. This article describes the importance of mathematics in the development of children with disabilities in preschool educational institutions, the experiences of pedagogues and neuropsychological kinesiological approaches to the development of mental processes in children.

Key words: pedagogical, neuropsychological, kinesiological, sensory.

СПОСОБЫ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ УРОКОВ МАТЕМАТИКИ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ С ДЕФЕКТАМИ

Аннотация. В данной статье описано значение математики в развитии детей с ограниченными возможностями в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях, опыт педагогов и нейropsихологические кинезиологические подходы к развитию психических процессов у детей.

Ключевые слова: педагогический, нейropsихологический, кинезиологический, сенсорный.

Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni o'qitish va tarbiyalashning ilmiy, moddiy va uslubiy bazasidagi o'zgarishlar tufayli jiddiy o'zgarishlar kuzatilmoqda.

Yangilanishning muhim shartlaridan biri innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish hisoblanadi. Bu bir tomondan, tuzatish-tarbiya jarayoning samaradorligini oshirishga, ikkinchi tomondan, o'quv jarayonida individual yondashuvni ko'proq qo'llashga imkon beradi.

Har bir alohida bola bilan ishlash samaradorligi har doim boshqacha. Bir bolada tuzatish jarayoni juda oson va samarali bo'ladi, boshqa bolada esa nutq terapeyasining turli bosqichlarida "tiqilib qolish" sodir bo'ladi. Nutq terapevtining ishi miya tuzilmalarning rivojlanish mantig'ini hisobga olgan holda differensial tarzda tuzilgan bo'lsa samarali bo'ladi. Nutq patologiyasi bo'lgan bolalar bilan tuzatish nutq terapeyasi ishining muvaffaqiyati ko'p jihatdan nutq buzilishlarini tuzatishga kompleks yondashuvga bog'liq.

So'ngi paytlarda logopediya amaliyotida neyropsixologiya kabi sohaga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Neyropsixologik tekshirish usullari maktabgacha yoshdagi nogiron bolalarda, shu jumladan og'ir nutqida nuqsonli bo'lgan (umumiy nutqning kam rivojlangan) bolalarda yuqori aqliy funksiyalarni tashxislash va tuzatish uchun muvaffaqiyatli qo'llaniladi.

Neyrogimnastika-bu vosita neyropsikologik tuzatish (yoki sensorimotor tuzatish) nomi.

Kinesiologiya-bu harakat orqali miya rivojlanishi haqidagi fan. Fiziologlarning tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, miyaning o'ng yarim shari- insonparvarlik, hayoliy, ijodiy –tana, harakatlarni muvofiqlashtirish, fazoviy vizual va kinestetik idrok uchun javobgardir. Miyaning chap yarim shari-matematik, ramziy, nutq, mantiqiy, analitik-eshitish ma'lumotlarni idrok etish, maqsadlarni belgilash va dasturlarini tuzish uchun javobgardir.

Neyrogimnastika mashqlarining har biri miyaning ma'lum bir qismini rag'batlantirishga yordam beradi va harakatni birlashtirish mexanizmini o'z ichiga oladi, shuningdek, harakatlar va psixofizik funksiyalarni muvofiqlashtirishni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Kinesiologik trening ta'sirida organizmda ijobiy tarkibiy o'zgarishlar yuz beradi. Nerv jarayonlarining kuchi, muvozanati, harakatchanligi, plastikliги yuqori darajada amalga oshiriladi. Asab tizimining tartibga soluvchi va muvofiqlashtiruvchi roli yaxshilanadi. Miya gimnastikasi insonning yashirin qobiliyatlarni aniqlash va uning miyasi imkoniyatlari chegaralarini kengaytirish imkonini beradi. Neyrogimnastika universal mashqlar tizimi bo'lib, u har qanday yoshdagi bolalar va kattalar uchun samarali.

Neyrogimnastika va kinesiologik o'yinlar va mashqlar yarim sharlar ishini sinxronlashtiradi, yodlashni yaxshilashga yordam beradi, suhbotdoshning (ota-onalar, o'qituvchi va boshqa bolalar) nutqini idrok etishni yaxshilaydi, bolaga doimiy qiziqish uyg'otadi, diqqatini faol ravishda jamlaydi, unga tezda harakat qilishga imkon beradi. Bir faoliyatdan boshqasiga o'tish, bu esa bolani darsga tez qo'shishga yordam beradi. Kinesiologik o'yinlar va vazifalar aqliy jarayonlarining rivojlanishiga foydali ta'sir ko'rsatadi: xotira, diqqat, fikrlash, idrok etish jarayonlari, fazoviy tasavvurlar va o'z-o'zini boshqarish jarayonlari. Muntazam mashg'ulotlar davomida hissiy fon barqarorlashadi, bolaning ichki salohiyati ochiladi va o'zini o'zi qadrlash darajasi oshadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda bolalar o'ynash, bir-biri bilan muloqot qilishdan zavqlanish, g'alaba qozonishga intilish, raqobatlash, kelajak uchun xatolarini hisobga olish orqali rivojlanadi.

Tarbiyachi ko'pincha mashg'ulotda diqqatni jamlash, ma'lumotni tartibga solish va eslab qolish, bir vazifadan ikkinchisiga tezda o'tishni qiyinlashtiradigan o'rganishda qiyinchiliklar va xulq-atvorda muammolar bo'lgan bolalarning e'tiboriga tushganligi aniq bo'ladi. Bunday bolalar doirasi ancha keng. Bular, shuningdek, diqqat yetishmasligi, giperaktivlik, impulsivlik kuchayishi, aqliy rivojlanishda turli kechikishlar va nuqsonlar bo'lgan bolalardir.

O'yin texnologiyalari qiziqish va motivatsiyani oshiradi, xatolardan qo'rqmaslikka va muloqotni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. O'yin har qanday bolaning tabiiy holati va ehtiyojidir.

Mutlaqo har qanday o'yin rivojlanish salohiyatiga ega. Agar o'yin neyropsixologik ekanligi ta'kidlangan bo'lsa, unda qoidalar kim uchun foydali bo'lishi va qaysi yoshdagi bolalar uchun tavsiya etilishini tavsiflashi kerak. Ko'pincha bu besh yosh va undan katta yoshdagilar. Shunday qilib ota-onalar bunday o'yinlarni mutaxassis maslahatisiz sotib olishlari mumkin-har qanday holatda ular foydali va qiziqarli.

Shunday qilib maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar uchun o'yinlar juda katta ahamiyatga ega: ular uchun o'yin-bu o'qish, ular uchun o'yin- bu mehnat, ular uchun o'yin bu jiddiy tarbiya shaklidir. O'yinlarning barcha turlari orasida bolani rivojlantirish uchun eng yaxshi ta'sir etadigani syujetli va rolli o'yinlardir. Bolalar uchun eng sevimli, eng kerakli o'yinlar bu shunday o'yinlarki,

unda bolalar o'zlari o'yin maqsadini belgilaydi. O'yin jarayoni ushbu maqsadga erishishdan iboratdir: bola reja tuzadi, amalga oshirish usullarini tanlaydi.

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